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Research Article

Formulation and Optimization of Esomeprazole Magnesium Buccal Films for Effective Treatment of Gastric Acid Reflux Disease

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ABSTRACT

The present study deals with the formulation and evaluation of fast-dissolving buccal films for effective treatment options in gastroesophageal reflux disease. The purpose of this study was to develop formulation and systematically evaluate in vitro performances of mucoadhesive patch films of Esomeprazole magnesium using, and PVP K30, PEG 400, to avoid gastric degradation and prolonging the release up to 8 h. Optimized formulation was carried out by using design expert in Quadratic model 13.0.5.0 version. The optimized formulation of films was subjected to an accelerated stability study and was found at 40°C/75% RH for 2 months according to ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Esomeprazole is a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) used for the treatment of gastric ulcers, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), Zollinger Ellison syndrome, erosive esophagitis long-term management of patients suffering from peptic ulcer and Helicobacter pylori infections alone or associated with other drugs such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.[1], The intragastric pH-monitoring data for esomeprazole,

20 mg once daily, show improvement over omeprazole, 20 mg once daily, but the esomeprazole, 40 mg once daily, intragastric pH data show a further convincing gain in control of gastric pH. [2]. Buccal films represent a recent advancement in buccal drug delivery, serving as semi-solid dosage forms that are applied to the buccal region and allowed to dissolve. [3], Following administration, they directly enter the

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systemic circulation. These films have quickly gained recognition as a novel administration route, offering improved safety and an enhanced onset of action. Buccal films are an elegant and efficient dosage form, providing superior bioavailability compared to other buccal dosage forms like buccal tablets, lozenges, and wafers. [4], This is achieved by bypassing the hepatic first-pass metabolism. Upon administration, these films dissolve within the patient's buccal mucosa. The oral mucosa serves as the site of drug administration and is further divided into buccal and sublingual mucosa. [5]

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Materials:

Esomeprazole magnesium, polyvinyl pyrrolidone K30 (PVP K30), and aspartame were purchased from Yarrow Chem Products Ltd, Mumbai, India. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) were purchased from Central Drug House (p) LTD, New Delhi. Citric acid was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Ethanol and distilled water were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Chemicals Ltd, Bangalore, India. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES:

Determination of the melting point of the drug:

The drug's melting point was determined by placing a small amount in a capillary tube closed at one end and placing it in Thiels' melting point apparatus. The temperature at which the drug melts was noted and the Reading was taken.

Solubility determination of drug:

The solubility of the Esomeprazole magnesium was dissolved in distilled water, methanol, ether, chloroform, and pH 6.8.

Drug excipients compatibility study:

Excipients are integral components of almost all pharmaceutical dosage forms. The successful formulation of a stable and effective dosage form depends on the careful selection of the excipients,

which are added to facilitate administration, promote the consistent release and bioavailability of the drug, and protect it from degradation. Infrared Spectroscopy is one of the most powerful analytical techniques to identify the functional group of a drug.

Method:

The pure drug and its formulation were subjected to IR studies. In the present study, the potassium bromide disc (pellet) method was employed.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR):

During preparation, the drug and the polymer may interact as they will be in close contact with each other which would affect the stability of the drug. The pure drug, polymer, and drug-polymer combinations and formulations were exposed to FT IR studies. The drug and/or polymer in a 1:1 ratio was taken. In the sample holder of the instrument, the mixtures were placed and the spectra were run from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} wave number. The FT-IR spectrum obtained for the pure drug was compared to the FT-IR spectrum of the drug with polymer.

Determination of absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of the drug:

Preparation of stock solution:

A stock solution of 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of esomeprazole into 100 ml of phosphate buffer. Then 20 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer 6.8, the calibration curve was prepared using an aliquot 2-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ from the stock solution.

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurate weight quantity of standard esomeprazole in 10 ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer, further diluted to get a working standard solution of 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Then 1,2,3,4... 10 ml, of working standard solution were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. Volume made up of 6,8 phosphate buffer solution. Then the sample was scanned in the UV range (200 – 400) peak maxima

were observed at 300.0 nm by using a UV-spectra photometer. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 300.0 nm against a blank and the calibration curve was plotted.

Method:

Solvent casting technique:

The mucoadhesive buccal film of Esomeprazole magnesium was prepared by a solvent-casting technique using a film-forming mucoadhesive polymer as per the formula given in Table 1. Initially, the polymers PVP K30 and PVA were weighed accurately and dissolved in 2 ml ethanol and 3 ml distilled water. The beaker containing polymers, ethanol, and water was kept aside for 15 min for swelling of polymers marketed as solution A. Then the polymeric solution was stirred for 1h on the magnetic stirrer to get a clear and bubbles-

free solution. Plasticizer PEG 400 was added to the polymeric solution A with continuous stirring. In another beaker, Esomeprazole magnesium with aspartame and citric acid was dissolved in a sufficient quantity of solvent (Ethanol: water 1:1) marketed as solution B. The solution was continuously stirred for 4 h. Then the drug-containing solution B and polymeric solution A with other excipients were mixed gently with the help of a magnetic stirrer to form the homogeneous casting solution. The whole solution was poured into the pre-lubricated glass petri-plate at 40 °C and left for 12 h. The film was removed carefully after drying and cut into 2×2 cm². The film was stored in butter paper covered with aluminum foil and stored at room temperature.

Table. No.1: Composition of mucoadhesive buccal films:

Sl. No.	Ingredients	Formulations Code											
		F1 (mg)	F2 (mg)	F3 (mg)	F4 (mg)	F5 (mg)	F6 (mg)	F7 (mg)	F8 (mg)	F9 (mg)	F10 (mg)	F11 (mg)	F12 (mg)
1	API	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
2	PVP K30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
3	PVA	35	35	35	40	40	45	40	50	50	50	55	55
4	PEG 400	5	5	4.7	5	6.3	6.3	6.3	7.8	6.3	7.8	5	7.8
5	Aspartame	20	20	20	20	15	20	20	25	20	15	25	20
6	Citric acid	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
7	Ethanol /Water(mL)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Evaluation of mucoadhesive oral films:

Thickness

It can be measured using a micrometer screw gauge at various locations. It is vital to assess the uniformity in film thickness as it directly impacts the accuracy of dosage in the strip.

Folding endurance:

The flexibility of the thin film is important when considering its breakage-free administration. The flexibility of the polymeric thin films can be measured by assessing their folding endurance. Folding endurance is determined by repetitively folding the film at a 180° angle in the same spot

until it breaks. A film that exhibits a folding endurance value of 300 or more is considered to have excellent flexibility. [6]

Surface pH:

To determine the surface pH, a combination of glass electrodes is utilized. The patches are placed in contact with 5 ml of distilled water for 1 hour. The pH can be determined by bringing the electrode near the surface of the formulations and allowing it to equilibrate for 1 minute. [7], [8]

Organoleptic properties:

The desired sensory characteristics such as color, flavor, and taste can be evaluated through visual

inspection of the film composition. E-tongue software helps assess the flavor intensity and determine the amount of flavor added, or if further adjustment is required. Uniformity in color and aroma, as well as an acceptable taste, enhance patient acceptance. [9]

Swelling study:

The oral patches are individually weighed (designated as W1) and placed in separate 2% agar gel plates, which are then incubated at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The patches are periodically removed from the gel plates and excess surface water is carefully eliminated using filter paper. The swollen patches are then reweighed (W2), and the swelling index (SI) is calculated using the following formula. [10]

$$\text{SI} = \frac{(W2 - W1) \times 100}{W1}$$

Drug Content Uniformity:

Drug content uniformity is determined by dissolving each patch in 10 ml of solvent and

filtering it using Whitman filter paper ($0.45 \mu\text{m}$). The filtrate is evaporated, and the remaining drug residue is dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). A 5 ml solution is diluted with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) up to 20 ml, filtered through a $0.45\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ Whitman filter paper, and the absorbance is measured using a UV Spectrophotometer against pH 6.8 phosphate buffer used as a blank. The experiments are conducted in triplicate, and the average values are reported. [11], [12]

In-vitro Drug Release Studies:

In vitro, drug diffusion investigations were carried out utilizing a Franz diffusion cell with a receptor compartment capacity of 150 ml. The dialysis membrane was installed in the diffusion cell's donor and receptor compartments. After positioning the film on the cellulose acetate membrane, it was wrapped in aluminum foil. Phosphate buffer, pH 6.8, was put into the diffusion cell's receptor compartment. [13]

Figure No.1: Franz diffusion cell

The entire assembly was secured to a hot plate magnetic stirrer, and the solution within the receptor compartment was continually mixed with magnetic beads while maintaining a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The samples were taken at various

intervals and subjected to spectrophotometric analysis to determine the drug concentration. Following each sample extraction, the receptor phase was refilled with an identical amount of phosphate buffer. [14], [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Organoleptic properties

Table. No.2: shows Organoleptic properties of esomeprazole magnesium.

Test	Specifications/ Limits	Observations
Color	Whitish Yellow	Whitish Yellow
Odor	Pungent	Pungent Oduor
Taste	Bitter	Bitter
Appearance	Powder	Powder

Determination of melting point:

The melting point of the obtained drug was found to be 168, which is within the reported range of 168–169. It complies with the standards, thus indicating the purity of the drug.

Solubility Determination:

Table.No.3: Solubility determination of esomeprazole magnesium.

SL. No	Solvent	Solubilities
1	Water	insoluble
2.	Methanol	Soluble
3	Ethanol	Soluble
5	0.1N HCL	insoluble
6	pH 6.8	soluble

Esomeprazole Magnesium was found to be insoluble in water. Esomeprazole magnesium is freely soluble in Methanol, Ethanol, and 6.8 pH phosphate buffer. Solubility analysis is important because the drug has to be dissolved in the solvents and also in the dissolution medium used.

Drug excipient compatibility studies by FTIR:

FTIR spectra of pure drug, polymer, and their physical mixtures (stored at 40°C 2°C / 75%+5% RH for 2 months) were recorded. The polymer and physical mixtures of drugs and polymers were scanned for absorbance which is shown in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4. The spectra obtained

from the physical mixtures showed all the principal peaks at or around the requisite wave number of pure drugs. Thus, it may be inferred that there was no interaction between the drug and polymer, the purity and integrity of the drug was maintained in the physical mixtures.

Figure. No.2: FTIR spectrum for pure drug of Esomeprazole Magnesium

Figure. No.3: FTIR spectrum for pure drug of Esomeprazole Magnesium with PEG 400

Figure. No.4: FTIR spectrum for pure drug of Esomeprazole Magnesium with PVP K30.

Determination λ of max:

Standard calibration curve of Esomeprazole in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

It was found that the estimation of Esomeprazole Magnesium by UV Spectrophotometrically method at max 285 nm in 6.8 pH phosphate Buffer

had good reproducibility and this method was used in the study. The correlation coefficient for the standard curve was found to be closer to 1 which is 0.9992, at the concentration range 10-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The regression equation generated was 0.011.

Table. No.4: Spectrophotometric data for the construction of the standard graph of Esomeprazole Magnesium in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at λ_{max} 300.0 Nm.

SL. NO	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance at 300.0 (nm)
1	0	0.000
2	2	0.065
3	4	0.114
4	6	0.177

5	8	0.233
6	10	0.290

Figure. No.5: Standard calibration curve of Esomeprazole Magnesium in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Evaluation of prepared mucoadhesive buccal films:

Film Thickness:

The thickness of the film-developed formulations F1 to F7 varied from 0.23 to 0.33 mm and was found to be uniform. The thickness increased with an increase in PVA concentration. The SD values were less than 1 for all formulations, an indication of more uniform films as shown (Table No.5).

Folding Endurance:

Folding Endurance of the developed formulations F1 to F7 varied from 114-165 as shown (Table No.5). Folding Endurance of the film increases with an increase in the PVA and PVP K30 Proportion.

Drug content uniformity:

Good uniformity in drug content was observed in all buccal films as shown (Table No.5). The drug content ranged from 93.82% - to 98.73%. Hence it was concluded that the drug was uniformly distributed in all the formulations.

Swelling index:

Figure No.26 shows the comparison of the Swelling index of the developed formulation F1 to F7 varied from 84.09% - to 95.03%. The Water Content remaining in F7 was found to be more so the formulation F7 which has a high % Swelling index was found to be 95.03%. The formulation F2 which has less % Swelling index was found to be 85.12% (Table No.5).

Surface pH

The surface pH was found to be in the range of 6.23 - 6.87 which is close to salivary pH, which indicates that films may have less potential to irritate the oral mucosa. The results are given in Table. No.5.

Disintegration time

Disintegration time of the developed formulations F1 to F7 varied from 25-44 as shown (Table No.5). Disintegration time of the film increases with an increase for the effect of polymers such as PVA and PVP K30 Proportion.

Table. No.5: Evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal film of esomeprazole magnesium:

Formulation Code	Drug content (%)	Swelling Index (%)	Surface pH	Folding Endurance (sec)	Disintegration Time (sec)	Film Thickness (mm)
F1	96.69±0.15	87.02±0.69	6.48±0.02	124±7.14	37.1±1.52	0.25±0.03
F2	95.10±0.13	85.12±2.50	6.83±0.10	114±5.88	31.5±0.12	0.23±0.05
F3	96.73±0.16	91.17±1.17	6.54±0.04	139±6.23	38.6±0.23	0.28±0.07
F4	98.53±0.18	86.04±3.51	6.48±0.06	165±8.12	44.2±0.18	0.33±0.06
F5	94.49±0.17	89.06±0.81	6.14±0.05	154±9.87	41.6±1.05	0.31±0.08
F6	95.76±0.10	93.15±4.91	6.23±0.12	126±4.56	34.3±3.09	0.26±0.02
F7	97.28±0.19	87.08±7.53	6.40±0.08	149±6.45	42.1±0.17	0.29±0.05
F8	96.82±0.10	95.01±5.35	6.47±0.13	125±5.29	34.2±2.12	0.22±0.09
F9	95.24±0.12	90.05±0.95	6.32±0.07	82±5.87	28.1±0.10	0.30±0.12
F10	95.92±0.20	94.10±1.88	6.45±0.13	97±7.55	29.6±4.06	0.27±0.15
F11	96.17±0.22	84.09±7.18	6.48±0.19	120±8.8	34.7±0.38	0.24±0.01
F12	93.82±0.19	88.13±3.83	6.33±0.20	75±9.45	25.2±1.15	0.32±0.04

Table. No.6: Comparative data percentage of in-vitro drug release for esomeprazole, buccal film F1-F6 formulations.

Time(min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	10.839	9.473	11.065	10.274	12.736	8.626
2	16.259	15.356	20.211	22.017	22.243	18.585
3	26.462	27.862	30.943	34.723	42.143	34.863
4	31.784	37.384	41.445	50.840	51.946	38.365
5	48.306	55.727	52.227	58.529	68.470	45.241
6	57.851	61.536	62.765	69.521	70.259	65.958
7	72.838	75.172	69.891	83.402	84.509	78.488
8	82.212	83.036	88.071	90.824	92.496	85.492

Figure. No.6: Comparison of in-vitro drug release formulation of esomeprazole buccal film F1-F6

Table. No.7: Comparative data of percentage in-vitro drug release for esomeprazole, buccal film F7-F12 formulations.

Time (hrs.)	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	11.065	10.726	11.403	11.516	13.661	13.097
2	15.920	17.162	23.937	22.356	29.695	24.389
3	38.769	32.623	44.944	40.463	43.264	44.664
4	43.405	40.745	53.766	51.386	58.527	59.227
5	48.448	54.607	67.490	56.149	68.470	68.750
6	66.695	68.292	71.610	61.170	73.453	71.733
7	78.980	76.524	82.544	79.595	82.176	85.738
8	86.193	85.160	93.601	89.915	91.637	93.970

Figure. No.7: Comparison of in vitro drug release formulation for F7-F12 of esomeprazole magnesium buccal film.

Accelerated stability studies for buccal film.

Table. No.8: Physicochemical properties of optimized formulation (F13) buccal film.

Time	Drug Release	Disintegration Time	Folding Endurance
Initial	84.63	30.16	77.40
1 Month	84.43	30.08	77.34
2 Month	84.73	30.12	77.65

Stability studies:

Stability studies for optimized formulation F13 were done to see the effect of temperature and humidity on buccal films while sealed in aluminum foil and stored in a stability chamber. buccal films were evaluated periodically (0 to 2

months) for disintegration time, folding endurance, and In vitro drug release. Table No.35 showed that there were no significant changes found in physicochemical parameters and in vitro diffusion of the most satisfactory formulations (F13) after the stability study.

CONCLUSION

The stability investigations conducted on Mucoadhesive Buccal Films did not yield any substantial alterations in their properties. These findings substantiate that the Mucoadhesive Buccal Films successfully withstood the rigors of stability testing under both ambient and accelerated storage conditions. The optimization and formulation of buccal films continue to evolve, driven by advances in pharmaceutical technology. Future research may focus on novel excipients, innovative drug release mechanisms, and personalized medicine applications. The findings of the drug-excipient compatibility FT-IR investigations revealed there was no chemical reaction between the excipients and the pure medication. The assessment criteria for Mucoadhesive Buccal Films, including Weigh Variation, Swelling Index, Moisture Content, Folding Endurance, Film Thickness, drug content, as well as in-vitro and in vivo drug release studies, were meticulously conducted. Remarkably, all these parameters were found to fall comfortably within the specified limits outlined in the Pharmacopoeia.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Shojaei AH. Buccal mucosa as a route for systemic drug delivery: a review. *J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 1998 Jan 1;1(1):15-30.
2. Kim D, Park MS, Yoo BW, Hong T, Park SJ, Kim CO. The safety, pharmacodynamics, and pharmacokinetics of immediate-release formulation containing esomeprazole 20 mg/sodium bicarbonate 800 mg in healthy adult male. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy.* 2019 Sep 3:3151-9.
3. Rajeshkumar VH, Ram D, Buddhadev S. Recent Trends and Advances in Buccal Film Drug Delivery System: An Innovative Pharmaceutical Dosage Form Technology.
4. Joshi R, Akram W, Chauhan R, Garud N. Thin films: a promising approach for drug delivery system. *InDrug Carriers* 2022 Mar 27. IntechOpen.
5. Montenegro-Nicolini M, Morales JO. Overview and future potential of buccal mucoadhesive films as drug delivery systems for biologics. *Aaps Pharmscitech.* 2017 Jan;18:3-14.
6. HAJU S, YADAV S, BAIG R, SAWANT G. Buccal film: A novel approach for oral mucosal drug delivery system. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2021 Jan 5:27-35.
7. Fonseca-Santos B, Chorilli M. An overview of polymeric dosage forms in buccal drug delivery: State of art, design of formulations and their in vivo performance evaluation. *Materials Science and Engineering: C.* 2018 May 1;86:129-43.
8. Davidovich-Pinhas M, Bianco-Peled H. Mucoadhesion: a review of characterization techniques. *Expert opinion on drug delivery.* 2010 Feb 1;7(2):259-71.
9. Choudhary A, Tiwari G, Pandey M, Kymonil KM, Saraf SA. Formulation and

- characterization of carvedilol buccal patches. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Sci.* 2010;1(4):396-401.
10. Zhang C, Liu Y, Li W, Gao P, Xiang D, Ren X, Liu D. Mucoadhesive buccal film containing ornidazole and dexamethasone for oral ulcers: in vitro and in vivo studies. *Pharmaceutical development and technology.* 2019 Jan 2;24(1):118-26.
 11. Singh A, Bali A. Formulation and characterization of transdermal patches for controlled delivery of duloxetine hydrochloride. *Journal of Analytical Science and Technology.* 2016 Dec;7:1-3.
 12. Shivalingam MR, Balasubramanian AR, Ramalingam KO. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patches of pantoprazole sodium. *Int J App Pharm.* 2021 Sep 7;31(5):287-91.
 13. Adrover A, Varani G, Paolicelli P, Petralito S, Di Muzio L, Casadei MA, Tho I. Experimental and modeling study of drug release from HPMC-based erodible oral thin films. *Pharmaceutics.* 2018 Nov 9;10(4):222.
 14. Verma R, Dewangan Y, Sahu L, Dongre B, Mishra K, Patel T, Nishad S, Damle A, Sahu G, DeviRao K, Mukta Agrawal M. Pharmaceutical Considerations behind the Development and Evaluation of Tablets. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2017;10(4):1230-8.
 15. Naik TS, Khale A, Kanekar H. Evaluation of mouth dissolving films: Physical and chemical methods. *Int. J. Pharm. Phytopharmacol. Res.* 2014;4(1):62-5.

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